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DYNAMIC MODELLING AND OPTIMAL CONTROL SCHEME OF WHEEL INVERTED PENDULUM FOR MOBILE ROBOT APPLICATION

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ABSTRACT

Unstable wheel inverted pendulum is modelled and controlled deploying Kane's method and optimal partial-state PID control scheme. A correct derivation of nonlinear mathematical model of a wheel inverted pendulum is obtained using a proper definition of the geometric context of active and inertia forces. Then the model is decoupled to two linear subsystems namely balancing and heading subsystems. Afterward partial-state PID controller is proposed and formulated to quadratic optimal regulation tuning method. It enables partial-state PID to be optimally tuned and guarantees a satisfactory level of states error and a realistic utilization of torque energy. Simulation and numerical analyses are carried out to analyse system's stability and to determine the performance of the proposed controller for mobile wheel inverted pendulum application.

KEYWORDS

Wheel inverted pendulum, Kane's method, partial-state PID, quadratic optimal regulation tuning

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A Time Series ANN Approach for Weather Forecasting

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Abstract:

Weather forecasting is most challenging problem around the world. There are various reason because of its experimented values in meteorology, but it is also a typical unbiased time series forecasting problem in scientific research. A lots of methods proposed by various scientists. The motive behind research is to predict more accurate. This paper contribute the same using artificial neural network (ANN) and simulated in MATLAB to predict two important weather parameters i.e. maximum and minimum temperature. The model has been trained using past 60 years of real data collected from(1901-1960) and tested over 40 years to forecast maximum and minimum temperature. The results based on mean square error function (MSE) confirm, this model which is based on multilayer perceptron has the potential to successful application to weather forecasting.

Keywords:

Artificial neural network, Multilayer perceptron, Time series analysis, Mean Square error function, MATLAB.

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ZIGBEE: A LOW POWER WIRELESS TECHNOLOGY FOR INDUSTRIAL APPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT:

The great potential of Wireless Sensor Network is being seen in industrial, consumer and commercial application. The wireless technology is becoming one of the most prominent areas of research. This paper focuses on the most widely used transceiver standard in Wireless Sensor Networks, a ZigBee technology. ZigBee over IEEE 802.15.4 defines specifications for low data rate WPAN (LR-WPAN) to support low power monitoring and controlling devices. This paper presents a Zigbee wireless standard, IEEE 802.15.4specification, ZigBee device types, the protocol stack architecture and its applications.

KEYWORDS:

ZigBee, IEEE802.15.4

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